

EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN ON THE BASIS OF FAMILY TRADITIONS

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Abstract: The article provides a detailed description of the upbringing of preschool children based on family traditions. In addition, detailed information is provided on the way in which our ancestors, in the social life of society, passed on to the new generation in the form of traditions, national, historical, labor, moral and spiritual experiences in family life, become a national tool for educating preschool children.

Keywords: tradition, value, national, upbringing, child, family, moral and spiritual experience.

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Abstract: The article describes in detail the upbringing of preschool children based on family traditions. Also, in the social life of the society, detailed information was given about the passing of national, historical, work, moral and spiritual experiences to the new generation in the form of traditions by our great ancestors in the family life, becoming a national tool for educating preschool children.

Key words: tradition, value, national, education, child, family, moral and spiritual experience.

Tradition is a social phenomenon in society, which can be defined as a set of general rules, rules and experiences that have found their place in the minds and lives of people, are passed down from generation to generation, and are used in family life. Family traditions are a social, mass phenomenon, which covers all

aspects of family life, that is, lifestyle, work, morality, culture, spirituality, and are passed down from generation to generation, are repeated, and are used. The scope, scope, and application of family traditions in life are relatively narrower than social traditions. From this perspective, family traditions differ from the traditions of state-level educational institutions and labor collectives in form, essence, content, and unique national characteristics.

Family traditions of the Uzbek people have their own national characteristics. Traditions decorate and express the family's lifestyle, enhancing its value. Each family tradition has its own form, content, goals and tasks. Family traditions differ from each other in their national content, form, essence and characteristics. They are a national educational tool that has a direct, systematic, continuous and strong educational impact on the formation of the younger generation. Family traditions are inextricably linked with the rich morals, culture, spirituality of the people and reflect them in their own way. The family traditions of the Uzbek family are reflected in the following areas: intellectual; moral; labor; refinement; law; economic; ecological.

The second main area of development in the "State Requirements for the Development of Early and Preschool Children" is "Socio-Emotional Development", which includes children's assimilation of moral norms, behavior in a team, and communication with adults and peers.

Preschool children: rules of hospitality; behavior in hospitality; greeting everyone; respect for elders and kindness to younger ones; asking how they are; helping when necessary.

All ideas, experiences, new customs, customs, spiritual and moral values that are instilled in children in the family are passed on through family traditions and serve to form them harmoniously. Family traditions closely help preschool children in applying the knowledge they receive in preschool educational organizations during classes on the environment, speech development, and familiarization with fiction.

The new generation continues all the life experiences of past ancestors to a certain extent through family traditions. The process of upbringing is multifaceted and, in fact, consists in passing on the knowledge, experience, skills and habits of older generations to the younger generation. Therefore, family traditions serve as a national educational tool in the upbringing of preschool children, in the implementation of the goals and objectives of family upbringing, and serve social education. When raising children in the family, it is of practical importance to use the national traditions accumulated in family life in a purposeful manner.

Indeed, in the social life of society, it is natural that the national, historical, labor, moral and spiritual experiences of our ancestors in family life are passed down to the new generation in the form of traditions, becoming a national means of educating preschool children. The most valuable aspect of traditions is that they should serve as a national means of education in preparing preschool children for family and social life. Family traditions acquire a more perfect and practical significance in the harmonious upbringing of preschool children, when they become the national spiritual and moral values of the people, passed down from generation to generation, from ancestors to generations.

Because family values have been and will remain valued and respected by the Uzbek people. Only when family traditions become spiritual and moral values will their educational and upbringing value and practical significance in the formation of students and youth increase.

That is why family traditions remain an educational tool in raising preschool children and preparing them for family life.

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